

The Shona Gender story communicated through Zimbabwean Star Frequency Modulation (FM) radio programme, *Umjolo*, the pandemic

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Abstract

Radio programmes are socialisation tools within communities and play a major role in shaping youth by reinforcing community gender ideologies and ethos. Since the programs are ideologically institutionalised structures, they serve to culture ethnic group members into their communities' ethos. In Zimbabwe, the Star FM radio program '*Umjolo, the pandemic*' addresses love-related dilemmas and fills an advisory void left by traditional Shona systems. By broadcasting these scenarios, '*Umjolo, the pandemic*' reinforces dominant gender discourses, sometimes to the detriment of marginalised groups. This paper employs the reconstruction theory to examine the gender-specific messages communicated through '*Umjolo, the pandemic*' radio programme and investigates whether these messages support or hinder Zimbabwe's drive towards gender equality by 2030. Using a multi-case study and both content and discourse analysis, the study explores how the programme shapes notions of gendered identity in contemporary Zimbabwe. The application of a grounded theory-based coding system allowed for the merging of salient sub-themes into a cohesive hierarchy of themes and subsequently global themes, and provided a structured analysis of the gender-related narratives broadcast on '*Umjolo, the pandemic*' radio programme. This attempt is important and timely as Zimbabwe nears its target of reaching gender equality by 2030. The study's main finding is that while '*Umjolo, the pandemic*' radio programme is culturally relevant, it often reinforces narratives that dehumanise, dewomanise and exploit women, which may hinder progress towards gender equality. The paper concludes by recommending further research into the broader impact of radio programmes on gender perceptions and equality goals in Zimbabwe.

Keywords

Umjolo, the pandemic, patched radio programme, *hot topics*, and gender equality.

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Introduction

The Shona people are a complex community. In this case, trying to understand the Shona wo/manhood gender disposition, as it is portrayed in the Star FM radio programme *Umjolo, the pandemic*, outside Shona gender ontology, may be futile. Shona gender relations are human and cultural discourses grounded in a Shona cultural milieu. In most cases, Shona participants interact within a Shona cultural frame of reference based on their community contexts. The Shona gender cultural frame of reference guides participants on appropriate gender interactions. African, Zimbabwean, and Shona gender discourses are marred by findings of female subordination and male dominance. These views have been informed by Western feminist gender discourses and by discourses in African history (Gaidzanwa, 1985; Taringa, 2018; Taringa, 2019). Little or no debate in the African and Shona gender discourse seems to deal with actual Shona cultural gender scenarios, such as those from *'Umjolo, the pandemic'* radio programme. The study added new knowledge in that it addresses an important and under-explored popular radio discourse, *'Umjolo, the pandemic'* and its influence on gender perceptions within Zimbabwean society. The article's engagement with locally grounded media content and Shona cultural contexts is particularly valuable in that it is unique. It offers useful insight into everyday gender negotiations in public media spaces. The paper is based on the assumption that gender personality traits depend largely on the gender diet imputed through socialisation during maturation, which forms the basis of an individual's gender identity. The radio programme serves as an aunt/uncle consultancy centre on love issues. The programme is named *'Umjolo, the pandemic'* since conflicts in relationships are on the rise; hence, they constitute a pandemic. It is code-named "*Hotsotso*", meaning "hot topics," in a jocular manner in Shona culture. The hosts choose the most complex situations that participants are experiencing and the dilemmas they may be facing.

Contextualising the article

This section establishes the basis for understanding "*Umjolo, the pandemic*," the Shona people; and Shona gender roles, aiding the reader's understanding. *'Umjolo, the pandemic'* is a Star FM radio programme about contentious romantic relationships. Taking over the role of the traditional Shona aunt/uncle, it offers a platform for relationship advice. While not professional counsellors, radio hosts act as mediators. Participants engage via phone, WhatsApp, and voice recordings.

The Shona people live in Zimbabwe and other Southern African countries, including Mozambique, Zambia, Malawi, South Africa, and Botswana. Shona groups include *vaKaranga*, *vaManyika*, *vaZezuru*, *vaKorekore*, and *vaKalanga* (Hachipolo, 1998). They are believed to have lived between the Limpopo and Zambezi rivers since 1500 AD. ChiShona is their identity and worldview. The Shona see everything in relation to humanity (Mbiti, 1969). Humanity keeps the ecosystem balanced. Shona society is patriarchal, privileging men and normalising violations of women's rights as masculine traits (Taringa & Taringa, 2018).

Principles guiding Shona gender relations

Gender is generally understood as a social construction of women’s and men’s roles in a given culture or location (Oakley, 1972; Pilcher & Whelham, 2004). Thus, gender roles are distinguished from sex roles, which are biologically determined (Haralambos & Holborn, 1995). Gender refers to both women and men, which departs from some previous studies that interpreted gender as referring to women’s conceptions only. Zimbabwean society encompasses egalitarian principles and is part of a bigger international community that is informed by the United Nations’ 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that aim to transform the world by supporting inclusive growth and sustainable development. Thus, in tandem with SDG 5, Zimbabwe aims to achieve gender equality by empowering all women and girls by 2030. Zimbabwe has shown commitment to gender equality through a number of steps. The country has a ministry focusing on gender, a gender equality provision in the Zimbabwe Constitution (The Government of Zimbabwe, 2013), and a national gender policy document. Gender commissioners are appointed by the President of Zimbabwe to oversee gender issues, thereby instituting an affirmative action policy in political, social, and economic circles in a bid to position women on the same level as men. Thus, this article explores whether the portrayal of Shona women is guided by the egalitarian principles of the Zimbabwean Constitution.

Gender, culture/tradition and “Umjolo” social media

Gender is not something we are born with nor something we have (West & Zimmerman, 1987) but something we do and perform during interactions with others (Butler, 1990; Taringa, 2018; Taringa et al., 2019). A person is born sexed naturally and gets gendered through socialisation and interactions in communities. Thus, sex precedes and informs gender. Therefore, sex is nature, while gender is nurture. Gender builds on physiology and anatomy, depending on the community’s gender role arrangements. There is no universal gender, though there is an understanding of sex that includes two bodies. The Star FM radio programme, ‘*Umjolo, the pandemic*’ has been singled out as a yardstick and a product of the Shona society’s socialisation of women and how women view themselves and are viewed by the opposite gender.

Neculaesei says that “culture influences thinking, language, and human behaviour” (2015, p. 31). The Shona culture influences the gender thinking, language, and behaviour of the participants of ‘*Umjolo, the pandemic*’ radio programme. According to Maluleke (2012), culture is like an umbrella under which some people like to hide from the rain and also to shade themselves from the sun. Every social group in the world has specific traditional, cultural, and religious rituals, practices, and beliefs, some of which benefit all members, while others may harm certain groups, such as women and children. Despite its violation of basic human rights and women’s rights, the gender aspects of this programme are neither questioned nor challenged. They are viewed as natural and biological when, in actual fact, they are social constructs (Taringa, 2014) that may be revisited, deconstructed, and reconstructed accordingly.

Culture has a negative impact on the dignity of women in most African communities. Tabane (2004) critiques culture as the culprit in the vulnerability of women to HIV/AIDS among the Batswana of Botswana. Maluleke (2012) excoriated culture for harbouring

harmful practices of early/forced marriages, virginity testing, widow's rituals, and breast sweeping and ironing that belittle women's rights. Zondi (2013) proffers that the cultural product of socialisation instils the superiority of male children while making female children responsible for the domestic space through patriarchal structures. Zondi (2013) further emphasises that, while gender issues are a universal concern, some societies are far more deeply affected than others. Cotton and Diala (2018) elucidate how culture presents most African states with a dilemma in crafting marriage laws as they become double-bound, compelled, on the one hand, to protect and affirm customary laws, which may include polygyny, while also being obliged to uphold women's rights to equality and non-discrimination. Hence, culture, in defiance of the constitution through its institutionalised structural systems, welcomes every newborn into the community. Eckert and McConnell (2015, p. 1) state that "we are surrounded by gender lore from the time we are born. This exploration involves putting on new lenses and seeing the Shona gender world anew through a constructivist ontology and an interpretivist epistemological view, which holds that there are multiple gender realities."

Social reconstruction theoretical framework and "Umjolo, the pandemic"

Social reconstruction theory explains this discourse. It is a lens for viewing Shona gender and wo/manhood traits, behaviours, and attitudes in 'Umjolo, the pandemic'. This theory serves as the study's framework and guides the conduct of research (Mpofu et al., 2013). The study suggests reviewing both positive and negative sides of the Shona personality. This can help build equality by improving the dignity of Shona women in Zimbabwe. The study creates a local gender framework set in Shona culture and religion. This builds indigenous responses, using local knowledge and practices to foster equality.

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Social reconstruction of culture makes culture relevant to day-to-day problems (Letsiou, 2014). Tradition is a set of beliefs, practices, and values inherited from the past that organises and regulates ways of living and makes sense of the world (Kanu, 2007). Through the social reconstruction theory, the Shona traditional, religio-cultural, and gender interaction value framework shapes and prepares Shona participants to manage their gender, courtship, love, and marriage relationships. The sudden disappearance of traditional family structures that provided the aunt/uncle narrative role has created a vacuum that the 'Umjolo, the pandemic' programme fills, but this needs to be premised on African culture. Hence, avoiding vetting the radio programme in the run-up to 2030 is tantamount to leaving the positive/negative portrayal of women and un/desirable gender socialisation of Shona women and men to chance.

The case study design provided the necessary in-depth understanding of the phenomenon, especially where little is known. An inductive qualitative case study combination is well-suited to a bounded unit of study, providing insights into the phenomenon (Creswell, 2009). The research used a revelatory case study strategy because it is designed to examine a unique case with no intention of generalising beyond the sample of seven scenarios. Murray and Beglar (2009, p. 48) view a case study as an "intensive, in-depth study of a specific individual or specific context or situation in great detail, while "in situ." According to Bryman (2012, p. 6), inductive theory is "a set of theoretical ideas driving the collection and analysis of data." The article also adopts an interpretivist epistemology,

in which reality is a social construction, and there are multiple realities (Morgan & Sakler, 2012). The article engages ‘Umjolo, the pandemic’ radio programme scenarios or views vis-à-vis gender relations, as understood from the viewpoint of the Shona themselves.

Ontologically, the analysis is informed by constructivism, where “there are varied and multiple truths, leading the researcher to look for a complexity of views rather than narrowing the few categories or ideas” (Creswell, 2009, p. 8). In tandem with this constructivist ontology, the article uses a revelatory case study methodology. The article is based on seven (7) Shona gender scenario texts aired and discussed on ‘Umjolo, the pandemic,’ a Star FM radio programme between January and April 2023, which reveal the Shona gender conception. The scenarios were critically analysed through discourse and content analysis to examine how they portray women and the implications for achieving a Shona community free of gender inequality by 2030. The small sample aligns with an in-depth study conducted by the researcher (Morgan & Sakler, 2012). This is a reasonable sample that aligns with a revelatory, unique case study as a starting point for theorising the devised Shona aunt/uncle phenomenon. Also, 16 participants who responded to the seven (7) ‘Hot topics’ scenarios were selected. Among the sixteen (16) participants, thirteen (13) were men, while only three (3) were women. The selection was particularly targeted at Shona scenarios, as the author is familiar with Shona culture.

The selection is made in line with Punch’s (2009, p. 162) assertion that “we cannot research everyone, everywhere, doing everything,” as the scope may be too wide. Therefore, the article makes use of a homogenous sample of seven (7) purposively sampled Shona gender scenarios that were broadcast as ‘Hot topics’, code-named “*Hotsotso*”, on Star FM in assessing how wo/manhood phenomena were gendered. Seven scenarios were chosen in which sixteen participants participated. The article triangulated textual critical content and discourse analyses of excerpts from purposively sampled scenarios that were transcribed from voice into text in the indigenous language Shona and rendered into English through literary translation. Punch (2009, p. 133) notes that “data collection and analysis are done in cycles and stop after two repetitions and even continue until theoretical saturation is achieved.” In line with Okinish and Tanaka (2023), the researcher recorded the narratives of both complainants and respondents. This allowed for listening to them several times and transcribing them verbatim. In analysing the collected data, the author used triangulated conventional content analysis to describe, interpret, and explain these relationships (Collins, 2011) in an attempt to account for Shona gender messages. Consistent with Asttride-Stirling (2001), the article adopts a thematic, web-like analysis of the data. It started with line-by-line open coding, then axial coding based on common words or phrases into sub-themes, themes, and global themes, which were combined into a coherent, reportable story on the gender message proffered and its implications for the possibility of reaching gender equality by 2030. Thus, the data are grouped into sub-themes, themes, and global themes based on the research questions to build up a coherent, reportable gender message proffered through the Star FM ‘Umjolo, the pandemic’ radio programme.

Presentation of Findings

The depiction in scenarios about ‘Hot topics, codenamed “*Hotsotso*, ‘*Umjolo*, the *pandemic*’, on the Star FM radio programme, is covered in the following seven (7) basic themes: womanhood is portrayed as an object of attraction or a model; not all women are the same; the woman participant perspective; women as undecided and victims of peer pressure; women are pictured as materialistic and untrustworthy; women are portrayed as products on auction and won by the highest bidder; a woman is portrayed as either “other” or “them”; and women as a labour force.

Womanhood is pictured as an object of attraction

In the following scenario, a woman is portrayed as an object of attraction, while a man serves as the observer who either praises or penalises her each time she makes a mistake. The two-dimensional gender pictures are explored below. Womanhood is determined by set patriarchal standards. The man is the subject who talks about the woman, while the woman is the object that is talked about. On the other hand, manhood is affirmed by their control of women. This brings tension as the woman is put under surveillance as the man tries to carve the woman he expects out of the real woman he has. The difference between what ought to be/is perceived and reality causes stress and anxiety for the men. As a result, men feel disrespected when women do not conform to the set patriarchal parameters. Hence, the husband complains to the aunt/uncle via the recreated narrative platform:

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“My wife, since I started dating her, was loving, slim, and beautiful. She started getting fat and growing ugly. She became a leopard and got fierce. She shouts at me that I have chosen to remain quiet. She now spends the whole day without taking a bath, pulling socks covering her head, and in pyjamas the whole day.”

The complainant (husband) brought complex gender dimensions that compromised a woman’s dignity and sense of equality. He complained that his wife had changed “... *getting fat and growing ugly*”. For this man, the woman started off as loving, beautiful and slim but had now grown “fat and ugly”. The view of this man commodifies women, making them ornamental. Women are often portrayed as emotional beings who are always shouting at their husbands. The woman in the scenario is equated to a “leopard” in terms of being aggressive “*She became a leopard and got fierce. She shouts at me that I have chosen to remain quiet.*” Women are also pictured as growing careless when they get married such that they no longer care about their looks, dressing or even hairdos: “*She now spends the whole day without taking a bath with pulling socks on her head and in pyjamas the whole day.*” Whilst the case is taken as evidence of women’s negligence, it is also a pointer to the stress and duress women undergo in the institution of marriage. The excerpt makes women objects for the male admiration or satisfaction and men as subjects and referees on women’s bodies and personalities. This is the same as the “othering” of women in a male-dominated, patriarchal world (De Beauvoir, 1974). The participants’ perceptions of womanhood carve a woman into an item of attraction according to patriarchal standards, as Taringa (2021) argues that love relationships trap women and make them second-class citizens. This perception may impact identity formation for women, who may measure

themselves against the social constructs of what an ideal woman should look like from men's perspectives.

Male participants' responses

“It is not a crime that a woman's body changes because of giving birth. Men, can you learn to be loving to your wives so that they continue respecting you?”

“Tell your wife what you want her to do so that you love her.”

“You, man, you are insane. You want to say the wife is now old, are you still the same?”

The first and third responses from three male respondents are in favour of the woman in question. They are in tandem with reconstructionism that aims to dislodge traditional masculinity. They accept that maturational processes are natural and beyond control. The scenario is warning partners in relationships to accept the changes that women naturally undergo. The participants are admitting that people do change naturally. One out of the three responses (the second one) suggests that people choose their natural body changes. The participants' views confirm Korhonen's (2006) observation regarding the way Bukowski's novels portray women as sex objects. Korhonen (2006, p. 17) comments that “most of the women in Bukowski's novels are portrayed as sexual objects, as if their worth is defined according to their appearances and looks.”

The woman participant's perspective

A female participant defended the lady in the above scenario. She argued that “*Some women are hardened by the marriage experiences. Some women get hardened through being troubled by men.*”

Male respondents kept on attacking the woman, saying a good woman will not be changed by circumstances:

“Even Lucifer was once an angel. Women are always like that, my sister. It is not true.”

“Lucifer was the most favoured angel of God.”

The women who sought to exonerate the woman in question by arguing that women are shaped by men. The respondents said that women “*hardened*” because of how they are treated by men. The gender dimension is that patriarchy shapes femininity. In the same scenario, culture disempowers women by empowering men. The male participant argued that women should remain good despite their circumstances. The insistence that women should remain upright even when wronged reinforces the stereotyping of women's tenderness. The biblical citation in this scenario resonates with Chitando and Chirongoma (2012), who decry the abuse of culture and religion by men in undermining the dignity of women.

Women are portrayed as undecided and as victims of peer pressure

A woman in this scenario is a testament to women's indecision. Her regretful response is a sign of a personality that succumbs to peer pressure. The first gender aspect is that the

lady's actions are dependent on her friends. The woman chooses to wrong her husband simply because her friends approve of this when she says that,

“Mukanya found out that I went to the funeral for my ex, James! Also, he realised that I sent him some money when he was unwell! So, Mukanya left me seated in the sitting room and told me to be gone by the time he comes back. What can I do, ladies, now that you are remaining quiet? Is it not that we agreed that I must go?”

The woman in the scenario appealed to her friends for help. Her worry was that her husband knew she had given money and attended the funeral of her ex-boyfriend. *“Mukanya found out that I went to the funeral for my ex, James! Also, he realised that I sent him some money when he was unwell.”* The lady appeared desperate since her friends were not forthcoming with much-needed advice: *“What can I do, ladies, now that you are remaining quiet?” Is it not that we agreed that I must go?”* She wished to prevent being chased away from home by her husband: *“So, Mukanya left me seated in the sitting room and told me that I should be gone by the time he comes back.”*

The male respondents in the programme told Mukanya to chase his wife away, while the shocking silence of the females on the platform may imply a lack of empowerment to confront the patriarchal and cultural challenges faced by women. This makes the platform a liability to the welfare and dignity of women. The scenario aligns with Sennott et al. (2021), who found that, in marriage, women value the support, social status, and respectability it offers but lament that *lobola* curtails their freedom and limits their autonomy. She could no longer visit her ex-boyfriend freely. The scenario affirms Maluleke's (2012) view that culture continues to disenfranchise women of their rights and freedoms. Holzhaeuser (2001) also describes women as entrapped. This scenario, therefore, reinforces the traditional gender status quo.

Participants' responses: “Women as undecided and victims of peer pressure”

“This lady should go to her family home, as she has shown that she still loves James.”

“Mukanya is a very soft person. If it were me, she should have gone already.”

“Haaaa! I think Mukanya is just feeling insecure. I do not think the lady still loves James, whom she calls her ex.

This lady is supposed to go back to her family home, as she still thinks like a child.”

“This lady needs to be battered like a snake that has gotten into the house. Mukanya is so merciful. This lady is possessed by demons. Why is it that she still loves her ex without becoming enemies? It means she still loves him. So, she should go there.”

The responses make men appear as managers who monitor women's behaviour in love relationships or courtships. Patriarchy privileges men in courtship, love, and marriage relationships. The patriarchal moral codes give them the unconstitutional right to

reprimand women. The four respondents' phrases (...*should go to her family home*, ... *should have gone already*, ...*thinks like a child*, and ...*needs to be battered like a snake*...) out of the five respondents' implicates this lady and contradict Oyewumi's (2010, p. 32) claim that “when the offender assaults a woman we should not be asked to run to his defense. If the victim is the Afrocentric sister or any sister, then if anything, we should rally to her defense.” The participants were not defending the woman whose dignity was at stake, as participants felt she had broken the moral code of the Shona community by sympathising with another man who was not her spouse. The same comments would not have been made if it were a man who said this. The traditional conception fuels gender-based violence, trauma, and the possibility of sexual harassment, thereby perpetuating inequalities between the two genders. Only one respondent captured in the sentence (*I think Mukanya is just feeling insecure*) supported the woman in question. The scenario debases the dignity of women amongst the Shona and Zimbabwean communities. The respondent, though not condoning the lady's behaviour, gives the benefit of the doubt. The scenario affirms Odu Yoye's (1995, p. 15) idea of “bringing into being new arrangements of gender reality.” The woman in the scenario begins to “weave a new pattern of womanhood” that seeks to discontinue patriarchal standards of womanhood (Odu Yoye, 1995, p. 16). She is a new woman who no longer feels used by an ex-boyfriend but rather feels like an equal. The scenario refutes Taringa et al. (2019), who argue for the possibility of women with wings who fly away from patriarchal confinement as the status of women continues to be downplayed (Badja, 2012).

Women are pictured as materialistic and untrustworthy

In the following scenario, a man came to the programme to have his woman publicly confess her love for him. He said,

“D.J., can you phone my girlfriend called Tariro. I love her. I also want to know whether she loves me the same. Tell her that I am her boyfriend. She should say my name. If she manages (John but not stated), give her this invoice so that she can go and collect her present at Croco Motors. She should simply say my name.”

The D.J. called the lady and said:

“Tariro, your loving boyfriend said he has bought you a present at Croco Motors. He said I should tell you that, ‘He is your beloved boyfriend.’ He said if you can say his name publicly, then I will give you an invoice to go and collect your present from Croco Motors.”

The excerpt brought in two gender dimensions. First, this man was not confident that the lady loved him: “*D.J., can you phone my girlfriend called Tariro. I love her. I also want to know whether she loves me the same.*” Second, this man tricked his girlfriend into finding out whether she truly loved him and him alone: “*He said if you can say his name publicly. He said if you say his name, you can take this invoice and go to Croco Motors to collect your present.*” The lady in the scenario had multiple relationships. She did not know her boyfriend's name because she had more than one. The boyfriend's doubt was confirmed as she misnamed her boyfriend:

“My boyfriend that loves me most.... It is ... ummmm, I am shy. Give me a clue. Maxwell! Is that so?”

The D.J. answered:

“No Tariro. You are lost. He is not Maxwell. He is John.”

The lady realised that she had made a grave mistake, and she lamented,

“Ooooo! God! My God! What a mess! I am so sorry, John. Pleease! Pardon me. Yuuuuuu! Ooooo!”

Men may know that they are not loved, but that they have what women want. Thus, they sometimes use the aspects admired by women to attract or frustrate women. The lady's responses carried two important gender undertones. First, her indecision indicated that she lacked confidence in what she was saying. She was unaware of the boyfriend who loved her the most. This was indicated in *“that loves me most.... It is ... ummmm, I am shy...”* Secondly, the fact that she asked for a clue, *“Give me a clue,”* was evidence enough that she did not know who the boyfriend was on the programme. The scenario confirms Gaidzanwa's (1985) observation that women are portrayed as harlots, and Chiweshe (2016) argues that women are commodified on the market.

Participants' responses: “Women are not trustworthy”

Male participants responded to this man's problem, while the women participants did not. As the woman in question was pleading and apologising, the women may have felt that this was humiliating.

“Man, there is nothing for you, man. There is someone who is at the heart of the lady. Your God and ancestors liberated you. If you are tying yourself back again, it is your choice. To say the wrong name and to struggle to come up with your name is evidence that she has many boyfriends, senior.”

“If it were me, that could have been the end of the relationship because she will continue doing it since she is used to doing that.”

“Not knowing you, brother, is a sign that she does not love you.” “How do you want her to divorce you?”

The gender message raised by the three participants above was that men can punish women and that women are victims. The phrases, *“...there is nothing for you, ...tying yourself back again; it is your choice, ...she has many boyfriends and ...she does not love you,”* imply masculine power in relationships and female subordination in love relationships. The scenario has implications that men can divorce women. The men did not advise the woman to choose who she loves or to divorce the boyfriend who humiliated her. It appeared to be the norm that love relationships are male-determined or engineered. It is men who decide whether the relationship continues. In this scenario, men are socio-

cultural referees, whereby women are constantly caught offside or portrayed as cultural deviants.

The above scenario is the direct opposite of the one below. The man in the scenario below felt that he was right to have two girlfriends at a time, as he was insecure and therefore needed another girlfriend:

“I have two girlfriends because they are not to be tampered with. I am not certain that the one I love most truly loves me. So, what I want is that, if she dumps me, I will go with the other one. If you are poor, the girlfriend may dump you or double-cross you. So, I will just act like a man.”

The participant in the above scenario justified having multiple partners: *“I have two girlfriends because they are not to be tampered with. I am not certain that the one I love most truly loves me.”* The scenario justified cheating to avoid disappointment if one of the ladies “dumps” him. This gentleman doubted the girlfriend he truly loved. So, he introduced an alternative girlfriend to serve his interests: *“So, what I want is that if she dumps me, I will go with the other.”* While this tells a gender story about women being unpredictable in courtship, love, and marriage relationships, it also tells a story about men’s insecurity. *“If you are poor, the girlfriend may dump you or double-cross you.”* The statement points to women as being materialistic by “dumping” poor men. In this man’s understanding, having multiple partners was a sign of manhood and virility: *“So, I will just act like a man.”* However, the following responses disapproved of the man having multiple partners:

“Trustworthiness begins with you, friend. Why are you doing what you do not want ladies not to do?”

“You know the truth, you know the one who loved you, and where you are just trying is clear.”

The two participants warned the young man to learn to be trustworthy by redefining and reconfiguring masculinity, thereby fostering gender equality in which men reciprocate. They argued for a transformative masculinity that fosters healthy courtship, love, relationships, and marriage. The scenario brings together two gender dimensions that challenge the traditional view that men are privileged in patriarchal society (Oyewumi, 2010). First, by encouraging men to adopt responsible masculinity that respects women, and second, by encouraging people to know who loves them. In this case, this young man was insecure because he knew he was not his partner’s first choice, which caused him stress that he articulated in *‘Umjolo, the pandemic.’* The advice of responsible masculinity is echoed by Chitando and Chirongoma (2012) in their reconstruction of participants’ gender conceptions.

Women are portrayed as products on auction, which are won by the highest bidder.

The scenario in this section depicts a woman as a commodity at auction, purchased by the highest bidder. The woman is chosen and has no choice. The portrayal brings in inter- and intra-gender images that not only show women as subordinates and victims but also show

that men are also victims when they are poor. The scenario labels women as falling in love with material possessions rather than men. This is captured in the following narration:

“My girlfriend was snatched by the sugar daddy who has a Fortuner. She is now coming back, begging me after two years. She is saying she had been cheated by the same sugar daddy who later dumped her when she got pregnant.”

In the above scenario, women were depicted as products to be auctioned off to the highest bidder. It commodifies women and makes them appear as if they are unable to make decisions. *“My girlfriend was snatched by the sugar daddy who has a Fortuner.”* The first dimension presents women as being attracted to people with money. The picture objectifies women as greedy. The second dimension makes men subjects of attraction depending on their belongings: *“She is now coming back begging me after two years. She is saying she had been cheated by the same sugar daddy who later dumped her when she got pregnant.”* Women’s dignity and welfare are negated by portraying them as gullible, naive, and greedy. Chiweshe (2016) agrees that women are commodified, which refutes Taringa et al. (2019), who note the reinvention of womanhood. This finding adds more evidence to Chitando and Chirongoma’s (2012) call for responsible masculinity. The portrayal of women in this scenario disempowers women and makes them objects for male exploitation.

Participants’ responses

“Friend, do not be underestimated like that. Tell her that you are sorry; the door to your heart has closed. Tell her that the two of you can always meet since you now know each other. You will keep seeing each other again. Tell her that she is not an Impala car that is sometimes hired.”

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This picture shows women who lose the love of their lives because they prefer wealthy men. Once women realise that they have been cheated, it may be too late for them to get back to the one who truly loved them. *“Tell her that you are sorry; the door to your heart has closed.”* Tell her that the two of you can always meet, since you now know each other.” Women are taken as pawns that men can manipulate according to their will. The likening of this woman to an Impala rental car is evidence that women are objectified and perceived as sex objects: *“Tell her that she is not an Impala car that is sometimes hired.”* The man knew that the girl did not love him, nor did he love her. The lady was just trapped by her love of financial security (Holzhaeuser, 2001; Sennott et al., 2021).

Women are portrayed as either “Other” or “Them”

A woman, despite getting married to a man, will continue being a stranger in the husband’s family. Her being married to a man does not make her the husband’s relative. Thus, she enjoys making decisions when her husband is still alive. That ascribed status ends with the death of her husband, as captured in the following excerpt:

“I am a 23-year-old lady. I married my husband two years ago, and we had a beautiful wedding. While we were enjoying our honeymoon, my husband told me that if he dies, he wants his body cremated. So, he passed on yesterday in his sleep, and the

postmortem revealed that he had a heart attack. I told his relatives, who refused to accept the decision, citing that there is nothing like that in the clan. Right now, they are making burial arrangements. What can I do? They do not believe me.”

The peers came in with advice for the troubled widow. The participants gave advice but avoided confrontation. The following responses were raised:

Participants’ responses: Women as either “Other” or “Them”

“The handling and disposal of the deceased’s body is a responsibility of the relatives. You played your part by telling them. It is difficult to convince them since it is simply your word against theirs, unless there was a will that documented how your husband wanted to be buried. In this case, chill down. You are not going to win. Let them bury their relative in accordance with their culture.”

“My daughter, what are you doing on radio, WhatsApp and Facebook while your husband is lying in state in the house in a coffin? Go and mourn your husband, and later come back to the programme.”

“Go back into the house! Leave the phone! Get away from radio, WhatsApp and Facebook; give your husband the last respect. He will never come back.”

“Please people do not attack her; she wants advice from the platform. If she comes after the burial of her husband, will she have an opportunity to retrieve the body from the grave for cremation?”

Participant who responded first, a male, felt that the widowed lady should adhere to her culture and allow relatives to bury the deceased in accordance with it. Only one respondent four felt that the widowed lady deserved to be advised on the platform “... *she wants advice*”. This was contrary to other participants two and three, who felt that coming to the programme while the deceased husband’s body was still lying in state was disrespectful of the dead, as captured in “...*Go and mourn your husband, and ...give your husband the last respect*”. This widowed lady was portrayed as having committed a taboo. The two women, in this case, showed more patriarchal attitudes than men. The gender message in the above passages confirms Chiweshe’s (2016, p. 231) assertion that “culture is a vehicle by which values are valorized and masculinity is transferred from generation to generation. Culture is used as an excuse for many cases of gender inequality.” Thus, women’s abuse is normalised under the guise of culture (Taringa & Taringa, 2018). The position adds evidence to Rafiq and Noureen’s (2015, p. 2) view that “men gain the position of transcendent subject whilst women are regarded as the other. Man is the subject, the absolute, while the woman is the other.”

Women are portrayed as ‘means’ and not ‘an end’ in themselves

The traditional perspective of viewing women as a labour force still perpetuates among the Shona people. This is captured in the following quote:

“My wife is lazy because she has the maid to do everything for her. Also, she treats the maid badly.” So, love deteriorates because of the irritation she causes me.”

To the complainant, his wife was a source of labour but was unfortunately lazy: *“My wife is lazy; she has the maid to do everything for her.”* He also stereotyped women as haters of other women, especially domestic workers: *“Also, she treats the maid badly.”* This man no longer loved his wife because he expected her to be a labour force: *“So, love deteriorates because of the irritation she causes.”* The gender tones carried in the scenario are that women are a labour force as wives or maids. The portrayal compromises the dignity of women in the Zimbabwean Shona society. In this case, men should learn to see women as ends in themselves, not as a labour force.

Participant responses: “Women as sources of labour”

There was only one participant who advised the complainant to see the difference between his wife and a maid. The scenario gives insights into the reality of the love relationships as the participant said:

“Hello father! Are you really aware of the difference between your wife and the maid? There is no love that fades with time. You have to know that you are a cheat.”

Patriarchal systems privilege men in this scenario, creating a sense of inequality between husband and wife. Such a relationship creates animosity between couples as the dignity of women is compromised. This confirms Hodgson and McCurdy’s (2001) view that men’s treatment of women should not be based on gender asymmetry.

Conclusion

Considering the purposefully sampled seven (7) gender scenarios from social media, it appears that Shona women are a blend of new and old perspectives on womanhood. Through such personas, the Zimbabwean community is witnessing a new woman who defines herself apart from the males in her life. This new womanhood is causing cultural shocks for male participants. While the phenomenon appears in a jocular, fictional manner, it is infiltrating the gender reality of Shona culture in many households across urban and rural communities. The voices of women emerging on the Zimbabwean traditional cultural gender platform feature a new woman who is prepared to challenge retrogressive traditional cultural gender arrangements that disenfranchise them of their rights and freedoms. Although this article shows how women are portrayed, it also has some limitations. It covers only seven scenarios on *‘Umjolo, the pandemic’* aired on Star FM. Hence, there is a need to investigate other programmes and other radio stations. Given this limitation, the article recommends that other studies use larger sample sizes and also assess the portrayal of men.

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